

MIXED CATION EFFECTS IN THE ESTIMATION OF BASE-EXCHANGE CAPACITIES OF HYDROGEN CLAYS

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In a number of previous publications (Mitra, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 555; J. N. Mukherjee, Mitra and S. Mukherjee, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, No. 10, 227; Mitra, S. Mukherjee and Bagchi, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1940, 10, 303; Mitra, *ibid.* p. 317; Mitra and Mitra, *ibid.*, p. 344; Mitra, *Bull. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1942, No. 4, 41) it has been shown that the base exchange capacity (B.E.C.) of a hydrogen clay is not a fixed quantity but depends on the p_H at which it is estimated and on the nature and concentration of cations introduced into the system in making the estimation. At a fixed p_H , e.g., $p_H 7.0$, the B.E.C. calculated from titration curves with different bases decreases in the order $Ca(OH)_2 > Ba(OH)_2 > NaOH$. When, however, the titration is carried out in the presence of a fixed concentration of the corresponding salts having a common anion, e.g., chlorides, the B.E.C. follows the order: $BaCl_2, Ba(OH)_2 > CaCl_2, Ca(OH)_2 > NaCl, NaOH$. The greater relative effect of Ca^{++} compared with Ba^{++} in the absence of salts constitutes an *irregular* or *specific* cation effect in the sense that the lyotrope series is not followed. In the presence of salts, the cation effect is *regular*. It has been found that the greater part of the reaction with the base takes place at a lower p_H when salts are present than when the bases alone are used. In the papers cited above these two types of cation effect have been reconciled in the light of the theory of the electrical double layer and of adsorption of ions assuming that in the presence of salts cations are adsorbed in a hydrated condition and when salts are absent, adsorption of more or less dehydrated cations takes place.

Other peculiarities of the cation effect, not clearly recognised by previous workers, have also been recorded and are discussed below. They were observed when the added salt had cations *other than those of the base* used for the titration. A clear understanding of such *mixed cation effects* is desirable as the soil adsorption complex usually contains more than one

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type of exchangeable cations and the part they may play, individually and relatively to each other, on the base exchange and other reactions of the complex is not definitely known. Some results obtained with a hydrogen clay from a black cotton soil from Padegaon are given in Table I. As B.E.C.'s at a fixed p_H , viz., p_H 7.0 have been compared, their variations arise only out of the peculiarities of the cation effect.

TABLE I.

*Base exchange capacity.*At p_H 7.0 in m.e. base per 100 g. H. clay with

System.	NaOH.	Ba(OH) ₂ .	Ca(OH) ₂ .
Sol+0.002N-NaCl	63.0	67.0	67.0
„ +0.002N-BaCl ₂	68.0	70.0	70.0
„ +0.002N-CaCl ₂	67.0	70.0	69.0
„ +0.1N-NaCl	80.0	87.0	85.0
„ +0.1N-BaCl ₂	114.0	122.0	119.0
„ +0.1N-CaCl ₂	110.0	120.0	116.5

The B.E.C. with a given base in the presence of a fixed concentration of different salts follows the order: $\text{BaCl}_2 > \text{CaCl}_2 > \text{NaCl}$ in agreement with the regular cation effect. The same order: $\text{Ba}^{++} > \text{Ca}^{++} > \text{Na}^+$ of the relative effects of the cations is also observed when different bases are used in conjunction with any one of the above salts; the B.E.C. follows the order: $\text{Ba(OH)}_2 > \text{Ca(OH)}_2 > \text{NaOH}$. It is interesting to note, however, that in the presence of either BaCl_2 or CaCl_2 , NaOH gives a smaller B.E.C. than Ba(OH)_2 or Ca(OH)_2 , although the concentration of the divalent cations cannot be materially different in the titration with the three bases. Some sort of an *ionic antagonism* between the comparatively few Na^+ ions on the one hand and the large number of Ba^{++} and Ca^{++} ions on the other, is indicated. The otherwise greater effect of the divalent cations and their capacity to displace acid from the colloidal particles appear to be somewhat inhibited by the Na^+ ions present at a much lower concentration.